

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10434124>

Abstract: This article discusses pedagogical aspects, uniqueness and methodology of professional competence development and role of motivation in higher education institutions.

Keywords: pedagogue, profession, teacher, speech etiquette, competence, method.

INTRODUCTION

Language learners can attain success by having their own goals and plans. Students can help themselves achieve their goals by determining their own language requirements. Setting goals and having expectation leads to increased motivation which resultantly leads to a higher level of language competence. The social and cultural changes taking place in the society ensured that the educational system acquired a new content in an evolutionary way, and educational values were formed that reflect advanced ideas. Universal, spiritual-ethical, professional values are significant in that they serve to educate the personality of the pedagogue, increase his dignity, and also help to form the skills of social activity. Therefore, the need to raise a competent person and qualified specialist becomes more urgent in the current conditions where new social relations are being decided in the developing world.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the end of the 1980s, the processes of active reforms in the system of training/training/education, retraining and professional development of teachers were initiated. Since then, this system has been considered as a single and integrated system of pedagogical education. Pedagogical education reforms started in 1990 under the Law on Education (1992; revised in 1995), against the background of the process of depoliticizing education, removing it from central and regional management, and democratizing school life. During this period, a tradition of abandoning a narrow professional approach to pedagogical education as an approach to pedagogical education was formed, the idea of the need for qualitatively new pedagogical education began to develop, and not only to solve narrow professional tasks, but also to be the subject of the educational process, in the acquisition of culture and its transfer the ability to be universal was its result.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development of new approaches to pedagogical education, such as democratization, humanization, fundamentalization (basic) of the content of training of specialists of Uzbekistan's higher education, ensuring the integrity of educational programs, the scope of ideology, elimination of influence, focus on universal values, creation of conditions for personal and professional development instead of formation ideology. General changes were made according to the tradition [1]. In general, pedagogic education reform was carried out based on three concepts, and each of them included working on a specific/concrete aspect of the innovative change process.

Modern innovative directions of pedagogical education include 1) development of own innovation theory; 2) person-oriented education;

3) a person-oriented-activity-based paradigm in the professional training/education of a pedagogue; 4) it is possible to distinguish the development of the organizational-structural model of education, the creation of a multi-level educational system.

1) Over the past decades, K. Angelovski, M.V. Klarin, V.Ya. Lyaudis, M.M. Potashnik, T.I. Shamova, O.T. Homericky, N.R. Yusufbekova, V.I. Zhuravlev, V.I. In the work of scientists like Zagvyazinsky, the first concept - the concept of pedagogical innovation is being actively developed [2].

In the process of receiving (providing) education at the higher education institution, identifying the specific features of the pedagogical professionalism of the future teacher and the opportunities for the formation and development of his innovative potential is provided by a number of higher education concepts (psycho-pedagogy, creative pedagogy, etc.). In the framework of our research work, the experience of creative activity serves as a priority direction of professional training (education) of students of a higher educational institution and one of the components of the content of their professional competence.

2) The second concept of person-oriented education is based on cultural-historical and activity-based approaches (J.I.C. Vygotsky, A.A. Leontev, D.B. Elkonin. E.V. Ilenkov, V.V. Davidov, G.P. Shchedrovitsky, A.G. Asmolov) and to date its general methodological development scientists: V.V. Serikov, V.G. Zuckerman, V.P. Zinchenko, J.H. Kulikova is; with this problem at the organizational-management level, M.N. Kostikova, V.A. Bolotovs are engaged.

The essence and meaning of the person-oriented concept can be expressed by the following interrelated (related) main points (theses). The main thesis is related to rethinking the role and place of science-based education/training in

pedagogic education: mastering (mastering) the science of teaching loses its status as a central task and becomes a tool for realizing the student's goals, a means of his development. Another idea of this concept is related to the construction of educational forms that are connected to the educational process (to the educational activity itself) and to its understanding (understanding) and the formation of the future teacher's personal pedagogical point of view. The main rules of this approach are defined in the following sequence: the person is the main value for himself and "others", education is the change of the person, which is carried out in the course of the integrated pedagogical process of higher education; the primary outcome of such education is not knowledge, skills, and abilities, but personal productivity focused on personal growth, empathic/compassionate interaction, and a high level of social engagement.

Due to natural and social reasons, the adolescent age of students is primarily sensitive to the rapid formation of self-awareness for goal-oriented self-determination in personal-social roles. In this regard, in the process of higher education, not only the "building up" of new knowledge and social experience takes place, but also its personal formation - self-education in accordance with one's own life strategy.

CONCLUSION

According to its content and organization, traditional pedagogical education sets the goal (intended) of training a specialist in a particular subject. In the educational system based on the activity-based approach, the educational process takes place within the framework of subject-object relations of its participants. The subject of influence - the teacher is placed in limited conditions, his activities and relations are strictly defined by the framework of the curriculum and programs. And the object - the student must be filled with a certain defined amount/volume of knowledge, his role is passive (passive) assimilation of data/information.

Pedagogical practice, and the needs of public schools in general, have long been associated with the need for traditional method specialists (one subject teacher). In this style, subject competence is the ultimate goal in the hierarchy of teacher training/teaching goals.

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